

RISK FACTORS AND EFFEKTS OF JAGUAR ALCOHOLIK ENERGY DRINK AND SPORTS ENERGY COCTAILIS FOR HUMAN HELTHR

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Аннотация: В данной статье изучен состав безалкогольных напитков, вместе с тем, разработаны и внедрены в таможенную систему современные методы определения кофеина и витаминов с методом газа жидкостной хроматографии. По результатам анализа выявлено, что безалкогольные энергетические напитки Yaguar и содержат чрезмерное количество кофеина. Такой «коктейль» негативно влияет на желудочно-кишечный тракт, раздражает слизистую оболочку желудка, при регулярном употреблении способствует развитию язвы желудка и других подобных заболеваний. А если рана уже есть, Jaguar только усугубит ее. В статье анализируется оборот некачественной контрафактной продукции на мировых рынках на примере зарубежных стран.

Annotation: This article analyzes the turnover of low-quality counterfeit products on world markets using the example of foreign countries. The negative impact of low-quality goods on human health and the economy of countries is substantiated. At the same time, modern methods for determining caffeine by liquid chromatography gas have been developed and introduced into the customs system. The analysis revealed that the non-alcoholic energy drinks Yaguar alcoholik and enerjy coctailis Such a "cocktail" has a negative effect on the gastrointestinal tract, irritates the mucous membrane of the stomach, and with regular use contributes to the development of stomach ulcers and other similar diseases. And if there is already a wound, Jaguar will only aggravate it. This article analyzes the turnover of low-quality counterfeit products on world markets using the example of foreign countries.

Ключевые слова: безалкогольные энергетические напитки Yaguar и содержат чрезмерное количество кофеина. Такой «коктейль» негативно влияет на желудочно-кишечный тракт, раздражает слизистую оболочку желудка, при регулярном употреблении способствует развитию язвы желудка и других подобных заболеваний. А если рана уже есть, Jaguar только усугубит ее. В статье анализируется оборот некачественной контрафактной продукции

Key words: non-alcoholic energy drinks Yaguar and contain excessive amounts of caffeine. Such a "cocktail" negatively affects the gastrointestinal tract, irritates the gastric mucosa, and with regular use contributes to the development of stomach ulcers and other similar diseases. And if the wound is already there, Jaguar will only make it worse. The article analyzes the turnover of low-quality counterfeit products

Why is carbon dioxide harmful in combination with alcohol and various additives? Such a "cocktail" has a negative effect on the gastrointestinal tract, irritates the mucous

membrane of the stomach, and with regular use contributes to the development of stomach ulcers and other similar diseases. And if there is already a wound, Jaguar will only aggravate it. There is a huge variety of alcoholic beverages. Conventionally, they can be divided into two categories: those that are created in order, roughly speaking, to get drunk, and those that are created to enjoy the taste and aroma. Jaguars, Grapes Days, Baltics and other similar drinks belong to the first category. Of course, you can get pleasure from them, but this pleasure is very specific. With very adverse long-term consequences, both for the one who receives this pleasure, and for others. Well, let's start with the Jaguar. This "cult" drink is very popular among Russians, which arose as a result of a relatively pleasant sweet taste (designed taking into account the preferences of our population) and a kind of intoxicating effect (let's say so). Well, the relative low price plays a role. The composition of Jaguar (since spring 2012) is as follows: purified water, sugar, ethyl lux alcohol, citric acid, Jaguar identical to natural flavor, mate tea leaf extract, taurine, caffeine, dyes - anthocyanin, caramel color and carmine, vitamins and natural flavor Astringency. The alcohol content is either 7% vol. or 5.5% vol. (depending on the version). Let's start with additives. Dyes - caramel color, anthocyanin and carmine - are harmless. Of course, there is no benefit from them, but there is no harm either. Nothing can be said for sure about flavorings, but they are clearly of artificial origin ("Astringency" is probably artificial for the most part). What the manufacturer means by "Jaguar" is not clear, let's hope that it is not the waste products of these animals. In any case, the presence of flavors is already alarming. I am silent about vitamins and mate tea extract: there is nothing wrong with them (although the guarana contained in mate in combination with alcohol will not bring anything good to your body, rather the opposite). Alcohol, of course, is harmful, as well as sugar - after all, the sugar content of 60 g / l cannot be called small. But the main harm and danger is still in the combination of alcohol, caffeine and taurine. There is a lot of caffeine in the Jaguar (as well as in its analogues, of which there are many - Revo, Red Devil and others) - 150 mg per can. Doctors recommend taking no more than 150 mg of caffeine per day; 500 mg is considered the maximum allowable limit. Thus, it is strongly not recommended to consume more than one can of Jaguar or a similar drink per day, this is even indicated by the manufacturer on its website. And taking four cans of Jaguar at a time already threatens with very serious consequences, up to resuscitation. Caffeine, taurine and guarana are harmful in themselves - subject to regular use. They create an increased load on the cardiovascular system, exhaust the body as a whole and the nervous system in particular, and can cause excessive irritability, fatigue, insomnia, and sleep disturbances. In addition, these substances are also addictive. A person simply cannot connect to activities without another dose of a caffeinated product. I'll note "in the margins": it seems to me that coffee addiction in Russia is gaining momentum; drinking several (three or more) cups of strong coffee during the working day already allows us to talk about mild addiction). However, in combination with alcohol, caffeine and similar substances become much more dangerous. It is worth noting that caffeine stimulates the nervous system, while alcohol depresses it. As a result, intoxication begins quickly and imperceptibly, and a peppy Jaguar lover can hardly control the amount of alcohol he drinks. And the load on the cardiovascular system is considerable. Moreover, those suffering from hypertension and some other diseases of the cardiovascular system have every chance of going to intensive care, and maybe straight to the next world. In addition, the nervous system, which is spurred on by caffeine and at the same time oppressed by alcohol, also experiences a great load. Brain cells (and not only brain

cells) work “for wear and Not to mention the simple degradation of mental abilities. In addition, manufacturers also carbonate alcoholic and energy drinks. Of course, not just like that. The fact is that carbon dioxide contributes to the accelerated absorption of alcohol into the blood and accelerated intoxication. It can be said that the average alcoholic energy drink is the fruit of an extremely cynical marketing study of the preferences of the target group of consumers. I will not indicate here who exactly belongs to this group, but simply give these preferences: so that the taste is sweet, the drink itself is easy to drink, and alcohol is almost not felt;

- to feel the rise of forces;
- to be intoxicated, and stronger and faster;
- so that the packaging (can) is beautiful and the name is attractive;
- so that the price is not too high. Why is carbon dioxide harmful in combination with alcohol and various additives like flavorings? The fact that such a “cocktail” negatively affects the gastrointestinal tract, irritates the gastric mucosa, and with regular use can contribute to the development of ulcers and other similar diseases. And if there is already an ulcer, then the Jaguar will only strengthen it. Thus, we can say that Jaguar, Red Devil, Revo and other similar cocktails cause great harm to health. Of course, something terrible is unlikely to happen from one can, but is it worth trying these dubious substances at all? They are produced precisely in order to bring the brain into a highly controversial state. This is not a wine or a high-quality cognac, which are created in order to enjoy taste and aroma in very limited doses. This is a typical mass product, and a very unethical product, as its manufacturers actually profit from the exploitation of human weaknesses. And finally, a special warning for those who suffer from diseases of the nervous system, the cardiovascular system, as well as the liver and gastrointestinal tract: do not try alcoenergy drinks at all, and if you use them, give them up as soon as possible! Yaguar Extreme DESCRIPTION C4 is the most powerful pre-workout complex that can maximize your performance, strength, endurance, make your workout intense and effective. The composition of the Extreme pre-workout mixture is represented by a variety of components and ingredients that will effectively increase the energy level, strength indicators, and create a long-lasting “pumping” effect. Each serving of the supplement contains 1.5 grams of beta-alanine, 1 gram of creatine nitrate, 1 gram of arginine-AKG, and 0.6 grams of a unique energy blend. Each serving of the supplement contains 1.5 grams of beta-alanine, 1 gram of creatine nitrate, 1 gram of arginine-AKG, and 0.6 grams of a unique energy blend. It is worth noting the excellent, refreshing taste of the additive, leaving a pleasant aftertaste of real fruit. The main components of the supplement: Mucuna Pruriens Mucuna pruriens is a velvet bean extract used to regulate and improve brain activity. In addition, this component reduces the level of cholesterol in the blood, increases energy levels, concentration and health. Synephrine HCL Synephrine hydrochloride is the main substance of orange extract, which can speed up metabolism. Its main function is to cause a feeling of coldness in the body, due to which more heat is produced, which contributes to the burning of adipose tissue and the increase in energy. In addition, sineferin stimulates the central nervous system, muscle performance, suppresses appetite. Creatine Nitrate The most important component of the supplement, which contributes to increased ATP synthesis and an improved anabolism process. Creatine Nitrate The most important component of the supplement, which contributes to increased ATP synthesis and an improved anabolism process. In addition, Creatine Nitrate promotes accelerated blood circulation and a long-lasting pump effect. Beta-

alanine Involved in the production of carnosine, which increases energy levels, improves anaerobic and aerobic endurance. It is worth noting that beta-alanine is able to suppress fatigue, through slowing down the production of lactic acid. You can read more about its action in the article "Beta-alanine: strength and endurance" Arginine AKG This ingredient is able to support the production of growth hormone and insulin, it also speeds up blood flow, providing a more efficient pump, due to the rapid delivery of oxygen and nutrients to the muscles. Caffeine is a powerful stimulant of the nervous system and energy production, thanks to it you do not feel tired, focus and concentration increase. Vitamin C Due to the fact that Vitamin C is included in the supplement C4 Extreme, the maximum duration of the action of the supplement is achieved. Xanthinol Nicotinate A form of Niacin that promotes increased energy and short-term explosive energy, improves memory. Xanthinol Nicotinate also speeds up metabolic processes, dilates blood vessels, thereby acting as a vasodilator. Folic acid. Folic acid is primarily needed to create and maintain new cells in a healthy state, so an increased content of folic acid is necessary for an improved body anabolism process. During a lack of folic acid, the bone marrow, which is responsible for active cell division, suffers, which negatively affects muscle growth.

itamin B12 supports and accelerates metabolism, participates in the production of fatty acids. In addition, vitamin B1 Jaguar (identification) and Yaga. low-alcohol carbonated energy drink Jaguar Aluminum drink 0.33 l, 9% Aluminum drink 0.33 l, 9% Founder of IBB Ltd. Castle 5.5-9 State will be released Period from [3016 days without source] Type low-alcohol carbonated energy drink Website jaguar-drink.com Composition (in descending order of component mass): water, sugar, ethyl alcohol, citric acid, mate leaf extract, taurine, caffeine, dyes: caramel, anthocyanin, carmine, natural flavor Astringency, various vitamins[4]. 100 ml of drink includes: carbohydrate 11.5 g caffeine 30 mg taurine 40 mg vitamins B1, B6 and PP ≈ 0.11 mg[4] Energy value - 100.4 kcal. 100 ml of drink includes:

Bibliography:

1. Lehtonen M.O. How to secure supply chains against counterfeit products using low-cost RFID: Dis. ... doc. of sciences. Helsinki University of Technology, 2009. [http:// e-collection.library.ethz.ch/eserv/eth:1234/eth-1234-02.pdf](http://e-collection.library.ethz.ch/eserv/eth:1234/eth-1234-02.pdf).
2. Counting the cost of counterfeiting. A Netnames Report. October 2015.
3. Estimating the global economic and social impacts of counterfeiting and piracy. Business Alliance to Stop Counterfeit and Piracy. Report 2011.
4. ITU, ITU releases 2014 ICT figures, 2014: https://www.itu.int/net/pressoffice/press_releases/2014/23.aspx
5. .NetNames, Internet 2020: an analysis of how new gTLDs will transform the Internet, Background research, 2014.
6. Michael B.G. Froman. Special 301 Report. // United States Trade Representative. 2018.
7. Report on the protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights in third countries. // Commission staff working document. Brussels, 1.7.2015. http://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/resources/documents/customs/customs_controls/counterfeit_piracy/statistics/2018_ipr_statistics.pdf.